

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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Contents

1	Executive summary	4
2	Conclusion & Results	4
3	Project objectives	4
4	Detailed report on the deliverable	6
4.1	The Target Groups for Exploitation Activities	7
4.2	Knowledge and Innovation Management	8
4.3	Exploitation standards	9
4.4	Exploitation activities	9
4.5	Sustainability beyond the lifetime of the project	11
5	References (Bibliography)	12
6	Dissemination and uptake	12
6.1	Uptake by the targeted audience	12
6.2	This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverable by the targeted audience	13
7	Deliverable timeliness	13
8	Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	13
9	Sustainability	13
9.1	Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects	13
10	Full track of dissemination activities	13
11	Full track of publications and IP	14

1 Executive summary

Building up on the communication and dissemination plan, we formulate a first plan for the exploitation of project results in nextGEMS. The major target group for the results uptake are the stakeholders that we have defined as the nextGEMS near and far field groups.

The nextGEMS' near-field stakeholder groups are the 'Users', 'Technologists' and the 'Earth-system Science Community'. These groups are invited to co-design the Science Challenge Problems used to structure the Knowledge Coproduction component of nextGEMS Hackathons. At the heart of the exploitation activities we find the project meetings in form of Hackathons to be most valuable in exploiting model development and emerging results among the near-field groups.

The nextGEMS' far-field stakeholder groups are the 'Broader User Community', the 'General Public and Media', and the 'Public-policy Community', among which the climate policy-makers and the younger generation as target group for capacity building around Next Generation Earth System Models will play an essential role.

Finally, nextGEMS also takes into consideration about the exploitation activities to sustain the project output beyond the lifetime of the Project.

2 Conclusion & Results

The exploitation plan described in this first report defines the measures that will be taken in the project to exploit project results in a sustainable manner and make them available during the development of the project and for the future research. The plan will help the nextGEMS consortium as well as the European Commission to ensure the adequate and timely planning of exploitation activities within this specific field. This is a living document and will be updated in month 30, together with the interim report, as well as in month 47 in the final report.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of NextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no

O2

To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:

- | | |
|--|----|
| (i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks; | no |
| (ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing; | no |
| (iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes; | no |
| (iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking; | no |
| (v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and | no |
| (vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take. | no |
-

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
Day to day project management	no
Scientific coordination including quality assurance (KPI) and risk assessment	no
Data management	no
Ensure efficient innovation management, managing exploitation of project results	yes
Supporting communication and dissemination activities	yes
Clustering with EC, regional and international projects/programmes	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

The European Commission defines *exploitation* in the Horizon 2020 work program as follows:

The utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

The Objective of the exploitation activities is among others to "effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn Research and Innovation actions into concrete value and impact for society".

Within the frame of nextGEMS we identified our stakeholder groups in near- and far-field and defined a strategy for knowledge and innovation management, which we see as a basis for any exploitation measures. Before anyone can make use of project results, such results need to be made available. Measures for disseminating project results range from scientific publications, presentation at conferences, meetings and workshops in form of hackathons, to policy briefs. These are stated in great detail in the nextGEMS Communication and Dissemination Plan (D10.2). To further facilitate the use of project results, we follow a list of exploitation activities including an active engagement of stakeholders from the renewable energy sector that we describe in more detail in the course of this report.

4.1 The Target Groups for Exploitation Activities

We distinguish the targeted audience and especially the target groups for exploitation activities in near and far fields.

nextGEMS works directly with the near-field stakeholder groups – the *'Users'*, *'Technologists'* and the *'Earth-system Science Community'* to co-design the Science Challenge Problems used to structure the Knowledge Coproduction component of NextGEMS Hackathons. Through these Challenge Problems different pilot-projects will be developed around nextGEMS *'Users'* in ways that also involve a broader community of Earth-system scientists.

Presently the *'User'* community involves the multi-national Spanish utility company IBERDROLA, acting also as one of the Beneficiaries of the consortium; the DTU (Technical University of Denmark) and VESTAS Wind Systems to explore re-newable (solar and wind) energy applications. A pilot on Fisheries will start in a later stage and build on a User group cultivated in previous and running European projects (PREFACE, AWA, and TRIATLAS) and will assess how mesoscale ocean variability affects the small pelagic fish dynamics as well as macro-zooplanktonic abundance in the Senegal-Mauritanian up-welling area in the Atlantic waters close to North West Africa.

'Technologists', particularly as Europe prepares for its first exascale machine, will be interested in the project's computational intensity, data management, post-processing, and analysis environments. Thus, nextGEMS will involve them taking part at technology scrums to help better understand workflow bottlenecks and how the value chain can be extended to seamlessly link to Machine Learning workflows.

Through the course of the project, nextGEMS open data and analysis frameworks will be exploited to expand the near-field user community. The Users of *'Earth-system Science Community'* engaged in the existing network such as the recently founded Centre of Excellence in High Performance Computing (CoE at the European level), Artificial Intelligence and Quantum Computing for Weather and Climate formally collaborating with hardware vendors Atos and NVIDIA, Horizon 2020 projects such as ESiWACE2 and ESiWACE3 (in preparation) could make use of the project results. We will coordinate scrums as cluster activities with the projects to strengthen exploitation of the project exercises and results.

Many of the nextGEMS developments are of interest to and can benefit from connections to the applied mathematicians. On the one hand, such links could be used to explore a novel Lagrangian approach to evaluate the models' representation of the West African Monsoon with an intricate interplay of large-scale circulation, deep convection, dust aerosol and ocean circulations. On the other hand, the rapidly growing Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence

community is providing an interdisciplinary mix of technologists and users to access and exploit the unprecedented data produced in nextGEMS. This is expected to become more intensive in the second phase of the project, when SR-ESMs will be extended to a broader range of Earth system processes and production simulations will be available. nextGEMS will seek additional users to help define problems to evaluate the links between hydrologic weather and the carbon cycle, natural hazards, and applications of new applied mathematics methods. The results of which, in turn, can be used by the mathematicians to evaluate the methods.

Among nextGEMS far-field stakeholder groups such as the ‘Broader User Community’, the ‘General Public and Media’, and the ‘Public-policy Community’, we concentrate on the interaction with *climate policy makers* and potential students for *capacity building* in the Earth-system science community. For the climate policy makers nextGEMS will provide policy briefs and contribution to various assessment activities organized by i.e. the IPCC, the IPBES and activities concerning the Food Security in West Africa. In addition, for capacity building purposes, nextGEMS will encourage students at the Master and PhD level to join the Hackathon activities to exploit the project methodologies and output. Beyond the Hackathons, nextGEMS will also support local educational entities to organize training activities to involve the interested younger generation, one first example being the student Hackathon at our partner institute UCM in Madrid in April 2022.

4.2 Knowledge and Innovation Management

We follow a strategy for knowledge and innovation management that makes gained data and knowledge available for the public good. We do not anticipate patentable or commercial products, instead, data and results shall be openly accessible following EC open data pilot and open access rules. In a first step towards this goal, we identified **pre-existing knowledge** of all beneficiaries within the Consortium Agreement. The protection of the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and the access rights have been regulated under section 8 and 9 of the document. Most of the model source code at the modelling centers, as well as further observational and model data at several other project parties are explicitly listed in the Consortium Agreement as background knowledge. We handle the Consortium Agreement as a piece of confidential document. In case of external request, and upon agreement with partners, information can be made available for specific request stating legitimate interest. In addition, the nextGEMS project office will fulfil its due diligence obligations to protect IPR in case any issues arise within the project (see also D11.1).

The Exploitation Plan is a living document. During the project lifetime we will create an **IP registry** for **foreground knowledge** obtained by nextGEMS, a table including any results co-developed within the project (see example table below). The IP Registry will be made available in the project website and in the updated report (D1.8, month 30).

Table **Example: Intellectual Property Registry:**

Results	WP	Del.	Dissemination	Background	TRL	Ownership	Protection	Exploitation
Result 1	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Result 2	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Result 3	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–

Table legend explained

WP: relevant work package(s)

Del: relevant deliverable No.

Dissemination: dissemination level of the result

Background: pre-existing knowledge relevant for the production of this result

TRL: Technical Readiness Level of the result

Ownership: draft of ownership for the result

Protection: preferred protection route for this foreground

Exploitation: preferred exploitation route for this foreground

4.3 Exploitation standards

The publication of data and results will be made freely and openly available to anyone with access to internet. The dissemination strategy has budgeted for and will prioritize the publication of results in open access journals and repositories. The scientific output of the project will also be made available through “nextGEMS community” in EC open repository ZENODO and OpenAIRE. Our community on Zenodo is reachable at <https://zenodo.org/communities/nextgems-h2020>. Further exploitation standards regarding data are described in detail in the nextGEMS Data Management Plan (D1.6).

4.4 Exploitation activities

Training and knowledge exchange with near-field groups

We involve members and stakeholders of the ‘*Earth-system Science Community*’, ‘*Users*’, and ‘*Technologists*’ to join the activity. In nextGEMS, we combine several efforts in our Hackathon meetings. By design, Hackathons are project meetings somewhere on the continuum between being formal and informal. *Formal* in a sense of having invited talks, high-level scientific discussions, workshops, trainings, and meetings to together define a plan for the next model development phase. *Informal* in the way how it’s done. We sit together in groups without hierarchies, “hack” our way through the latest simulation output while discussing bugs and features for which there is always an expert around. The format of such meetings is the key to their success. Mutual training and knowledge exchange fosters the sustainability of emerging results.

In particular, we started to involve ‘*Users*’ from the beginning of the project through our project partner IBERDROLA. Based on a first knowledge exchange between project scientists, technologists and IBERDROLA on solar energy application during and following the Cycle 1 Hackathon, we continuously extended the ‘*Users*’ group from renewable energy to include other stakeholders from this sector. At the end of April we will meet with several parties from the solar- and wind energy sector to continue knowledge co-production, plan further exploitation activities and invite stakeholders to the upcoming Cycle 2 Hackathon. The engagement of these ‘*Users*’ in the Hackathon will ensure provision of useful and usable model outputs that can be exploited by the renewable energy sector and support their planning activities, adaptation, competitiveness, and more efficient production of sustainable energy.

Training and knowledge exchange with far-field groups

As part of our interaction with the far-field stakeholder group we organise training and capacity building among external early-career scientists on the Master and PhD level. In the Cycle 1

Hackathon we included especially PhD students from project partner's institutes that were interested in working with the new simulation output. While they got to know the data infrastructure and were able to collaborate on scientific tasks together with young and senior scientists from the project, the project itself took great benefit out of their feedback on the data handling, as well as bugs and features in the model simulations. Many of them stay connected and further co-develop data workflows and model improvements at the different institutes.

Motivated by their first hackathon experience, the PIs from our partner institute University of Madrid (UCM) hold another hackathon for their Master students. Supported by local professors as well as project scientists and technologists, 19 students were analysing Earth system features that climate models often struggle to properly represent and were using the most recent available model output. Despite the general struggle such large model output provides, the students were managing their tasks with great success and some will even join us in the Cycle 2 hackathon. For our Cycle 2 hackathon we opened a call for stipends for students at the Master and PhD level to join us in Vienna end of June 2022. Applications were reaching us from several European countries as well as from abroad and from people with exceptional programming skills and either a background in renewable energy or climate science. 15 students are selected and invited to join us in Vienna and cluster with experts from the renewable energy sector to work on a defined *Challenge Problem* related to renewable energy, in particular solar and wind energy application.

Next to students and users from the renewable energy sector, we additionally invite the 'Broader User Community' and the 'Public-policy Community' interested in the renewable energy from a policy perspective, including climate change mitigation and adaptation. The latter will be involved through workshops and interviews, where we will discuss the role of climate information in future energy planning and policy and start developing the nextGEMS *Renewable Energy Storyline*.

Clustering with other projects of the near-field group

The Horizon 2020 project [EUCP](#) is coming to an end and in a joint meeting with nextGEMS PIs and scientists we were able to exchange ideas / approaches and especially lessons-learned concerning EUCP user engagement on their way to producing actionable climate information for risk-based planning. While this was a helpful first exchange, we will further engage in the final EUCP multi-user forum beginning of May 2022.

However, our main cluster activities happen again at hackathons, which provide the possibility to meet with the climate and weather community from parallel projects, such as ESiWACE2 (EC H2020), ESiWACE3 (EC Horizon Europe, planning phase), the WarmWorld initiative (Germany, BMBF), and DestinE (ECMWF, planning phase). Technical tools and data standards are co-developed and thus useful for a broader community and by default more sustainable. None of the internal and external project partners is obliged to use a specific tool, but rather may continuously choose the best options. Such a co-development without prioritisation will automatically focus on the most useful candidates and result in a truly useful and high-level product similar to many open-source developments.

nextGEMS puts a focus on clustering with two specific stakeholder groups, renewable energies and fisheries. Both sectors play important roles in a sustainable energy and food supply in a changing climate. Through knowledge exchange and co-production we aim to design useful information for those sectors based on a new generation of Earth system models that are able to resolve climate and weather features at the relevant scales.

Good data practice

Concerning standardization, we focus on good data practice and in-depth descriptions of data

handling as part of the openly accessible online book [easy.gems](#). [easy.gems](#) provides not only information on the simulations conducted during nextGEMS, but also includes a range of example scripts for working with the model output and tips and tricks for fast and elegant processing with CDO (Climate Data Operators) and in Python. [easy.gems](#) will be further described in the upcoming deliverable D2.1. [easy.gems](#) builds upon efforts in a predecessor project to nextGEMS, the DYAMOND project, and it is thought to be an open and collaborative book including descriptions of specific simulations, but also collects and develops generally applicable tools to handle new km-scale climate model output. It is therefore our main exploitation activity in terms of improved data handling and is planned to be continued after the project ends in further projects mentioned above and thus, serves as project legacy to nextGEMS as well as all collaborating projects.

Vlog entries

In a last point we would like to mention the exploitation potential of our nextGEMS video blog (Vlog). In particular the *Progress*, *Research* and *Results* videos will promote and ease access to project results and hence improve and ensure their exploitation.

4.5 Sustainability beyond the lifetime of the project

The exploitation plans outlined above, the ongoing activities together with the mentioned communication and dissemination plan, as well as the co-production plan and the data management plan are all designed to sustain the impact of the project well beyond the project lifetime. In addition to the exploitation plan and the standard knowledge and innovation management, the two most important ways in which nextGEMS will ensure its legacy arises out of the basic design of nextGEMS itself. Our global objective O1 has at its heart the idea of advancing and maintaining European leadership in the development of a new coordinated Earth-system modelling capability.

O1: to develop two SR-ESMs for applications (i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations; (ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and (iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol.

In particular, we join forces in bringing two European models for climate prediction to work on a storm-resolving scale. This will lay the foundation for those models to remain one of the world's best and most efficient climate models in the coming decades and foster climate research in Europe. nextGEMS model developments will be clustered with further highly-ambitious national and international projects such as DestinE (ECMEF international funding scheme), WarmWorld (BMBF German funding scheme), and ESiWACE (the EC and national funding scheme). The clustering clearly increases nextGEMS's scientific prospects for success and leads to a sustainable development beyond the lifetime of the project.

Another component making nextGEMS a sustainable project is described by our objective O3, which endeavours to create a new Earth-system modelling culture through the involvement of a much broader spectrum of expertise than is generally available within the present model-centred approach to model development.

O3: to build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by: (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve Knowledge Coproduction.

Stakeholders from the climate application sector will engage in our hackathon meetings from an early point in the project and co-develop tool and relevant output for their respective application. nextGEMS is not aiming directly at any commercial use. However, the training and co-development with the application sector provides huge potential for future tools and analysis in particular in two important areas, that is renewable energies and fisheries. More general, climate simulations at km-scale open up great potential for more targeted climate policy and concrete added value for adaptation measures and thus for society.

By meeting these objectives, nextGEMS will influence the European culture of Earthsystem modelling, as well as its roadmap for high-performance computing and data science.

5 References (Bibliography)

See references, especially links in the text.

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverable by the targeted audience

The deliverable will be openly accessible from the EC website. This report in particular is less important to be disseminated, while it's content, the described exploitation of project activities and results will reach the respective audience by design.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes

We were in exchange with the nextGEMS EC coordinator.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

No changes.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The Exploitation Plan builds upon the Communication and Dissemination Plan stated in deliverable D10.2 and the Data Management Plan D1.6. Through it's strong dependence on the project Hackathons, it is also linked to all research themes and all deliverables related to Hackathons.

For improved model development as well as to better exploit the project capabilities and results, nextGEMS clusters with other projects such as EUCP, DestinE, WarmWorld, and ESIWACE.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon, 19.10. - 22.10.2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - Activity: NextCalendArt 2022
- Joint meeting of nextGEMS and the EUCP: EUCP is another H2020 project that is about to end and that shared with us their successful and less successful stories concerning user interaction.
- UCM Student Hackathon, 1.-3.4.2022 near Madrid

11 Full track of publications and IP

No publications so far.